

EFFICIENT EXTRACTION OF CLOSED MOTIVIC PATTERNS IN MULTI-DIMENSIONAL SYMBOLIC REPRESENTATIONS OF MUSIC

Olivier Lartillot
University of Jyväskylä
Department of Music

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present an efficient model for discovering repeated patterns in symbolic representations of music. Combinatorial redundancy inherent to the pattern discovery paradigm is usually filtered through global selective mechanisms, based on pattern frequency and length. Our approach is based instead on the concept of closed pattern, insuring lossless reduction by adaptively selecting most specific descriptions in the multi-dimensional parametric space. A notion of cyclic pattern is introduced, allowing the filtering of another form of combinatorial redundancy provoked by successive repetitions of patterns. The use of cyclic patterns implies a necessary chronological scanning of the piece, and the addition of mechanisms formalizing particular Gestalt principles. This study shows therefore that the automated analyses of music cannot rely on simple mathematical or statistical approaches, but need rather a complex and detailed modeling of the cognitive system ruling the listening processes. The resulting algorithm is able to offer for the first time compact and relevant motivic analyses of simple monodies, and may therefore be applied to automated indexing of symbolic music databases. Numerous additional mechanisms need to be added in order to consider all aspects of music expression, including polyphony and complex motivic transformations.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper is focused on automated description of symbolic music, and presents an efficient algorithm for discovering repeated patterns. Repeated patterns are structures easily perceived by listeners, experienced or not, and represent therefore one of the most salient characteristics of musical works, sometimes called *parallelism* [8]. In this paper, patterns will be searched from symbolic representations of music rather than from audio signals. A pattern extraction task on the symbolic level, although theoretically simpler, remains extremely difficult to carry out, and its automation has not been achieved up to now. Indeed, computer researches on this subject hardly offer results close to listeners' or musicologists' expectations. Hence the pattern discovery task is so complex that it cannot be fulfilled directly from the audio signal, without a prior transcription from the audio to the symbolic representations, in order to carry out the analysis on a conceptual level.

We previously showed that the pattern discovery task leads to a problem of combinatorial redundancy, which needs to be carefully controlled [6]. We proposed therefore a heuristic based on maximally specific description of pattern classes, that may in fact be related to the concept of *closed pattern* [12]. We also introduced a notion of implication relation between multi-dimensional pattern description, that may be related to the subconcept-superconcept relation defined in the *Formal Concept Analysis* (FCA) theory [5], and that comes from the Galois connection between pattern description and pattern classes. We showed elsewhere the necessity to model the phenomenon of pattern cyclicity [7]. This idea will be defined more precisely in the second part of this paper, which will also present an extension of the subconcept-superconcept relation to cyclic patterns, enabling a simple modelling and efficient control of the complex structural configurations found in every musical piece, even simple ones.

2. CLOSED PATTERN DISCOVERY

This section presents the basic problem of pattern discovery and introduces the notion of closed pattern.

2.1. Definitions

Let $S = \langle a_1 a_2 \dots a_N \rangle$ be a sequence of elements of some set $a_i \in A$. A *subsequence* $S_{i,l}$ of index $i \in [1, N]$ and of length $l \in [1, N + 1 - i]$ is the sequence :

$$S_{i,l} = \langle a_i a_{i+1} \dots a_{i+l-1} \rangle. \quad (1)$$

We say that a subsequence $S_{i,k}$ is *included* in another subsequence $S_{j,l}$, and we write $S_{i,k} \subset S_{j,l}$ if $i \geq j$ and $j+l \leq i+k$. We may then propose a first simple definition of a *pattern* $P \in \mathcal{P}(S)$ of length l :

$$P \in \mathcal{P}(S) \iff \exists (i, j) \in [1, N]^2, P = S_{i,l} = S_{j,l}. \quad (2)$$

The *support* of a pattern P , denoted $\sigma(P)$, is the number of occurrences of that pattern, i.e.

$$\sigma(P) = \left| \{ i \in [1, N], S_{i,l} = P \} \right|. \quad (3)$$

2.2. Redundancy Filtering

The task of discovering repeated patterns leads to combinatorial problems, that have been considered in particular

in the Frequent Itemset Mining (FIM) community. For each pattern $P \in \mathcal{P}(S)$, all its $2^l - 2$ subsequences Q are also patterns of S :

$$(P \in \mathcal{P}(S) \text{ and } Q \subset P) \Rightarrow Q \in \mathcal{P}(S). \quad (4)$$

All these subpatterns are therefore explicitly discovered by any basic pattern discovery algorithm [12]. One common way to solve this problem consists in focusing on *maximal patterns* P of the sequence S , denoted $P \in \mathcal{M}(S)$, that are patterns of S not included into any other pattern of S :

$$P \in \mathcal{M}(S) \iff \left\{ \begin{array}{l} P \in \mathcal{P}(S) \\ \nexists Q \in \mathcal{P}(S), P \subset Q. \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

This heuristic enables a significant reduction of the number of discovered pattern, but leads also to a loss of information. Indeed, not all the subpatterns may be immediately reconstructed knowing the maximal patterns. For instance, the gray subpattern in figure 1 is redundant as it can be simply retrieved as a suffix of the black pattern. However, in figure 2, the same gray subpattern is not redundant any more, because its support (4) is larger than the support of the black pattern (2).

Figure 1. The gray subpattern is not a closed pattern: it is a simple suffix of the black pattern.

Figure 2. The gray subpattern is now closed: its support is bigger than the support of the black pattern.

A pattern P will be called *closed*, denoted $P \in \mathcal{C}(S)$, if and only if there exists no proper superpattern Q of same support :

$$P \in \mathcal{C}(S) \iff \left\{ \begin{array}{l} P \in \mathcal{P}(S) \\ \nexists Q \in \mathcal{P}(S), \left\{ \begin{array}{l} P \subset Q \\ \sigma(P) = \sigma(Q). \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

The set of closed patterns give a compact and lossless description of a sequence.

2.3. An Incremental and Chronological Approach

Our approach to discovering closed patterns in musical sequences is *incremental* and *chronological*. This will be justified in section 4, showing the necessity to model successive repetitions of a same pattern as a traversal through

one single cyclic pattern, and hence to consider a chronological approach of music.

A detailed and illustrated description of the algorithm has been presented in [6].

2.3.1. Incremental approach

The successive prefixes of each pattern are discovered progressively: they are considered as successive *intermediary states* of a *pattern chain* (PC) whose final state represents the whole pattern. At each step of the progressive construction, all the occurrences of the last discovered prefix are considered. Identical continuations form new extensions of the prefix, represented as children of the current state. Since each state can accept several children, the set of all patterns form a tree, called *pattern tree* (PT). The explicit representation of prefixes as intermediary states of pattern chains induces a simply linear complexity: each pattern of length l is represented by l states (which is significantly lower than the 2^{l-2} non-closed subpatterns).

Similarly, each pattern occurrence is also represented as a chain of states called *pattern occurrence chain* (POC) featuring the successive prefixes too. Each state of a POC is related to its corresponding PC. As each pattern occurrence can also accept several different possible continuations, the set of all pattern occurrences that are initiated by one note forms a tree, called *pattern occurrence tree* (POT). The root of each POT is associated to the root of the PT (node a in figure 4), which represents the simple concept of note, and is therefore called *note pattern*. Since all notes can potentially initiate a POT, they are all occurrences of the note pattern.

The inclusion relation between patterns may be decomposed as a product of two sub-relations: prefix and suffix relations. Any subpattern will then be considered as a prefix of a suffix of a pattern. The closure of a pattern P may then be assessed following these two relations.

1. Pattern P is *prefix-closed* if there does not exist pattern Q of which P is a prefix of same support.
2. The remaining, and most complex, part of the study concerns patterns in suffix relations. Pattern P is *suffix-closed* if there does not exist any pattern Q of which P is a suffix of same support. Consider a pattern P' , which has been discovered as an extension of its prefix P . The set of patterns Q' of which P' is a suffix is simply constructed from the set of patterns Q of which P is a suffix.

2.3.2. Chronological approach

The pattern discovery process is chronological: the main routine of the algorithm consists in a single traversal of the sequence S , from the first element a_i to the last element a_N . Each new element a_i induces an update of the whole pattern tree.

For this purpose, hash-tables memorise all the possible *continuations* of P , that is, all the possible elements appearing just after each of its occurrence. If a previous

occurrence of pattern P has been continued by an element identical to a_i , then an extension P' of pattern P may be discovered (if not already) and represented as one of its child. The suffix-closed condition should however apply: there should not exist a pattern Q' of which P' is a suffix of same support. During the chronological analysis, a pattern P' that was first considered as non-closed may become closed once discovering a new occurrence that is not an occurrence of the superpattern Q' (an example will be shown in paragraph 3.3). Superpatterns Q' can easily be retrieved, as extensions of the corresponding superpatterns Q of P by the same element a_i . Not all the superpatterns Q need to be considered, but only those containing an occurrence concluded by previous element a_{i-1} .

3. MULTI-DIMENSIONAL CLOSED PATTERNS

In previous subsection, pattern was searched in sequences of elements $S = \langle a_1 a_2 \dots a_N \rangle, a_i \in A$. Music, on the contrary, is expressed in a multi-dimensional parametric space.

3.1. Multi-Parametric Description of Music

The model presented in this paper only analyses monodic sequences, i.e. successions of notes without superposition. We can therefore represent any monodic sequence as previously :

$$S = \langle n_1 n_2 \dots n_N \rangle, n_i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{N} is the parametric space of notes. In our model, this note space is simply reduced to :

$$\mathcal{N} = \text{diat} \times \text{chro} \times \text{rhyt} \quad (8)$$

where

- diat, or *diatonic pitch space*, represents pitches as positions in the implicit tonal scale. Diatonic transpositions will be detected in this space.
- chro, or *chromatic pitch space*, represents pitches as positions on the piano keyboard. Following the MIDI standard, with middle C is associated the value 60.
- rhyt, or *metrical space*, represents temporal positions in term of the distance from the beginning of the musical sequence. The rhythmic unit of the metrical space is given by the time signature.

The pattern discovery task cannot be directly applied on this note sequence S , because each successive note is related to a distinct metrical position and is therefore distinct. Even if the metrical space is discarded, neither rhythmic patterns nor transposed melodic patterns may be discovered. Most computational approaches, including ours, model therefore musical sequences as a succession of intervals between successive notes :

$$S = (\overrightarrow{n_1 n_2} \succ \overrightarrow{n_2 n_3} \succ \dots \succ \overrightarrow{n_{N-1} n_N}). \quad (9)$$

An interval $\overrightarrow{n_i n_{i+1}} \in \overline{\mathcal{N}}$ is a vector between two points of the note space \mathcal{N}

$$\begin{aligned} n_i &= (\text{diat} = d_i, \text{chro} = c_i, \text{rhyt} = t_i) \\ n_{i+1} &= (\text{diat} = d_{i+1}, \text{chro} = c_{i+1}, \text{rhyt} = t_{i+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and can therefore be described by the three coordinates :

$$\overrightarrow{n_i n_{i+1}} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{diat}(\overrightarrow{n_i n_{i+1}}) \\ \text{chro}(\overrightarrow{n_i n_{i+1}}) \\ \text{rhyt}(\overrightarrow{n_i n_{i+1}}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} d_{i+1} - d_i \\ c_{i+1} - c_i \\ t_{i+1} - t_i \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

Figure 3. Multi-dimensional description of a musical sequence, which contains two occurrences of a pattern $abcde$.

3.2. Formal Context Representation of Patterns

We will represent musical patterns with the help of a conceptual framework that defines *objects* associated with different kinds of *attributes* [5]. These attributes consist not only of the different musical dimensions, but also of the different subpatterns and superpatterns. Following the incremental and chronological approach explained in paragraph 2.3, we can restrict our study of the inclusion relations between patterns to suffix relations. In this respect the objects of the pattern descriptions are the successive notes of the musical sequence forming the set $\mathcal{N}(S)$. Each note $n_i \in \mathcal{N}(S)$ relates to a specific *temporal context*, defined by *the part of the musical sequence concluded by this note* n_i .

Each note n_i is described firstly by the different musical characteristics of the preceding interval: $\overrightarrow{n_{i-1} n_i}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\text{desc}}^{0,d}(n_i) : \text{desc}(\overrightarrow{n_{i-1} n_i}) = d, \\ \text{desc} \in \{\text{diat}, \text{chro}, \text{rhyt}\}, d \in \text{desc}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Each note n_i is also described by the musical characteristics of the previous intervals:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\text{desc}}^{j,d}(n_i) = \text{desc}(\overrightarrow{n_{i-j-1} n_{i-j}}) = d, \\ \text{desc} \in \{\text{diat}, \text{chro}, \text{rhyt}\}, d \in \text{desc}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Then the pattern description of the sequence S may be expressed as a *formal context* $(\mathcal{N}(S), \mathcal{D}, I)$ where :

- the set of *objects* is $\mathcal{N}(S)$: the set of notes in S ,

- the set of *attributes* is \mathcal{D} : the set of elementary musical descriptions defined by equations 12 and 13,
- and I is the binary relation between $\mathcal{N}(S)$ and \mathcal{D} , called *incidence*, defined by:

$$(n_i, d) \in I \iff d(n_i) \text{ is true.} \quad (14)$$

We then define the *derived description* C' of a set of notes $C \subset \mathcal{N}(S)$ as the common description of all these notes:

$$C' = \{d \in \mathcal{D} \mid \forall n \in C, (n, d) \in I\}. \quad (15)$$

The notes in C are therefore occurrences of a same pattern, which is maximally described by C' .

Is dually defined the *derived class* D' of a description $D \subset \mathcal{D}$ as the following class :

$$D' = \{n \in \mathcal{N}(S) \mid \forall d \in D, (n, d) \in I\}. \quad (16)$$

The pattern discovery task consists in finding exhaustive class D' sharing a same description D . The trouble is, lots of different descriptions D_i may lead to same classes D'_i .

3.3. Formal Concept Representation of Patterns

The *derivators operations* defined by equation 15 and 16 establish a Gallois connection between the power set lattices on $\mathcal{N}(S)$ and \mathcal{D} . The Gallois connection leads to a dual isomorphism between two closure systems, whose elements, called *formal concept* of $(S(S), \mathcal{D}, I)$ corresponds exactly to the *close patterns* $P = (C, D)$, verifying:

$$C \subset \mathcal{N}(S), D \subset \mathcal{D}, C' = D, \text{ and } D' = C. \quad (17)$$

For a close pattern $P = (C, D)$, C is called the *extent* of D and D the *intent* of C . We may simply call C and D respectively the *class* and the *description* of P .

Hence, for a set of patterns $P_i = (D'_i, D_i)$ of same class $D'_i = C$, the close pattern $P = (C, D)$ is described using the derived operator C' defined in equation 15: it contains all the elementary descriptions common to all notes of the class C . In other words, closed patterns are described as precisely as possible. However, as listeners tend to perceive only repetition of connex subsequences, we should select only the descriptions of the longest set of contiguous intervals $(\mathcal{D}^j \succ \mathcal{D}^{j-1} \succ \dots \succ \mathcal{D}^0)$ leading to the context note and discard older descriptions \mathcal{D}^{j+k} if there is no description \mathcal{D}^{j+1} associated to step $j + 1$. We have proposed a further continuity constraint, that seems to correspond more deeply to listeners perception, stating that contiguous intervals should be described by same dimensions.

$$\forall i \in [1, j], \exists \text{desc} \in \{\text{diat}, \text{chro}, \text{rhyt}\}, \quad (18)$$

$$\exists (d, d') \in \text{desc}^2, \mathcal{D}_{\text{desc}}^{j,d} \text{ and } \mathcal{D}_{\text{desc}}^{j-1,d'}$$

Closed patterns, as formal concepts, are naturally ordered by the *subconcept-superconcept* relation defined by

$$(C_1, D_1) < (C_2, D_2) \iff C_1 \subset C_2 \text{ (} \iff D_2 \subset D_1 \text{)}. \quad (19)$$

(C_1, D_1) may therefore be considered as *more specific* than (C_2, D_2) .

The incremental and chronological pattern discovery methodology presented in section 2.3 may be generalized using this multi-parametric definition of closed pattern. For instance, pattern $a \succ b \succ c \succ d \succ e$ (more simply denoted e), in figure 4, features melodic and rhythmic descriptions:

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \text{diat} = 0 \\ \text{rhyt} = .5 \end{array} \succ \begin{array}{l} \text{diat} = 0 \\ \text{rhyt} = .5 \end{array} \succ \begin{array}{l} \text{diat} = -2 \\ \text{rhyt} = .5 \end{array} \succ \begin{array}{l} \text{diat} = -2 \\ \text{rhyt} = 4 \end{array} \right)$$

whereas pattern $a \succ f \succ g \succ h \succ i$ (or i) only features its rhythmic part:

$$(\text{rhyt} = .5 \succ \text{rhyt} = .5 \succ \text{rhyt} = .5 \succ \text{rhyt} = 4).$$

Hence pattern e is more specific than pattern i . When only the two first occurrences are analyzed, as both patterns have same support, only the more specific pattern e should be explicitly represented. But the less specific pattern i will be represented once the last occurrence is discovered, since it is not an occurrence of the more specific pattern e .

Figure 4. The rhythmic pattern $afghi$ is less specific than the melodic-rhythmic pattern $abcde$.

3.4. Optimal score description

In order to reduce the space complexity of the pattern representation, and also to simplify as much as possible the pattern description of the musical score, to each closed pattern $P = (C, D)$ will be associated a *specific class* $SC(P)$ which consists of the set of occurrences that are not included into classes of more specific patterns:

$$SC(P) = C \setminus \bigcup_{(C', D') < (C, D)} C'. \quad (20)$$

Reversely, the general pattern classes may be retrieved through an union of its specific class and the union of the specific classes of all the more specific patterns :

$$C = SC(P) \cup \bigcup_{P' < P} SC(P'). \quad (21)$$

During the chronological analysis of the musical score, only the specific classes are constructed. But each time a specific pattern occurrence is discovered, all the less specific patterns need to be recalled by the algorithm, because their extensions may lead to the discovery of new specific

patterns. For instance, in figure 5, groups 1 and 3 are occurrences of pattern h , and groups 3 and 4 are occurrences of pattern d . Since pattern d is more specific, the less specific pattern h does not need to be associated with group 4 (that is why it is represented in gray). However in order to detect groups 2 and 5 as occurrences of pattern l , it is necessary to implicitly consider group 4 as an occurrence of pattern h . Hence, even if pattern h , since less specific than d , was not explicitly associated with group 4, it had to be considered implicitly in order to construct pattern l . Implicit information is reconstituted through a traversal of the pattern network along the subconcept-superconcept relations.

Figure 5. Group 4 can be simply considered as occurrence of pattern d . However, in order to detect group 5 as occurrence of pattern l , it is necessary to implicitly infer group 4 as occurrence of pattern h too.

3.5. Generalization of patterns

New patterns can be discovered as simple generalizations of already known patterns. In bar 7 of figure 6, the two first notes form an occurrence of pattern h described by $\text{diat} = +1$ and $\text{rhyt} = 1$. The third note cannot however fulfill the known extension of pattern h into pattern i with description $\text{diat} = 0$ and $\text{rhyt} = 2$, because the melodic description $\text{diat} = 0$ does not fit here. However, as the rhythmic description $\text{rhyt} = 2$ fits, a new extension j is discovered as a generalization of pattern i .

The less specific patterns, although usually not explicitly represented in the analysis, should be updated if necessary. In particular, when a generalization of a pattern is discovered, the generalization of all its more general patterns should also be considered. For instance, as i has been generalized into j , it should also be inferred that c is generalized into k in the same way. In this way, the analysis of the next bar (8) consists simply in recognizing this general pattern k already known.

4. CYCLIC PATTERNS

In this section, we present another important factor of redundancy that, contrary to closed patterns, has not been studied in current general algorithmic researches.

Figure 6. Progressive discovery of the pattern repetitions on the score and the resulting pattern tree (below the score). The generalization of pattern i (bar 6) into pattern j (bar 7) leads to the implicit generalization of pattern c into pattern k , than can therefore be immediately identified in bar 8.

4.1. Redundancy Due to Successive Repetitions

Combinatory explosion can be caused by successive repetitions of a same pattern (for instance the pattern $a \succ b \succ c$ in figure 7, of description ($\text{rhyt} = 1 \succ \text{rhyt} = 2$)). As each occurrence is followed by the beginning of a new occurrence, each pattern can be extended (leading to pattern d of description ($\text{rhyt} = 1 \succ \text{rhyt} = 2 \succ \text{rhyt} = 1$)) by a new interval whose description ($\text{rhyt} = 1$) is identical to the description of the first interval of the same pattern (i.e., pattern b). This extension can be prolonged recursively (into e, f , etc.), leading to a combinatorial explosion of patterns that are not perceived due to their complex intertwining.

Figure 7. Multiple successive repetitions of pattern abc form a complex intertwining of non-perceived structures.

4.2. Cyclic Patterns

Our representation (figure 7) shows that the last state of each occurrence of pattern c is synchronized to the first state of the following occurrence. Listeners seem to tend to fusion these two states, and to perceive a loop from the last state (c) to the first state (a) (figure 8). The initial acyclic pattern $a \succ b \succ c$ leads therefore to a cyclic pattern that oscillates between two states $b' \cup c'$, corresponding to rhythmic values 1 and 2. Indeed, when listening to the remainder of the rhythmic sequence, we actually perceive this progressive oscillation between these two states b' and c' . Hence this cycle-based modeling explains a

common listening strategy, and resolves the problem of combinatorial redundancy.

Figure 8. The successive repetitions of pattern $a \succ b \succ c$ lead to its cyclicity, hence to an oscillation between states $b' \circ c'$.

This cyclic PC $b' \circ c'$ is considered as a continuation of the original acyclic PC $a \succ b \succ c$ (figure 8). Indeed, the first repetition of the rhythmic period is not perceived as a period as such but rather as a simple pattern: its successive notes are simply linked to the progressive states a , b and c of the acyclic PC. On the contrary, the following notes extends the POC, which cannot therefore be associated to the acyclic PC anymore, and are therefore linked to the successive states of the PC (b' and c'). The whole periodic sequence constitutes then a single POC representing the traversal of the acyclic PC followed by the cyclic PC.

It can be remarked also that, by property of the cyclic PC, no segmentation is explicitly represented between successive repetitions. The periodic sequence in figure 8 can be perceived for instance as formed by successive repetitions of a rhythmic period composed of a succession of a quaver and a crochet, or in the contrary a succession of a crochet and a quaver. Indeed, the listener may be inclined to segment at any phase of the cyclic PC (or not to segment at all).

This additional concept immediately solves the redundancy problem described in the beginning of this section. Indeed, the unique POC that is progressively extended is more specific than its suffixes, which cannot therefore be extended any more.

This phenomenon of successive repetition, although very frequent in musical expression, has been rarely studied [2]. The combinatorial explosion generated by the phenomenon is reduced by selecting, once the analyses is done, the patterns featuring minimal temporal overlapping between occurrences. As the selection is inferred globally, relevant patterns may be discarded. Besides combinatorial redundancy remained problematic since the filtering is done after the actual analysis phase. Our considering of local configurations enables a more precise filtering.

4.3. General and Specific Cycles

The specificity relation defined in previous section needs to be applied to cyclic patterns too: a cyclic pattern C would be considered as more specific than another cyclic pattern D when the sequence of description of pattern D is included in the sequence of description of pattern C . Here too, this concept of specificity plays a pivotal role in music perception and enables a sound algorithmic processing of music.

Figure 9. More detailed analysis of the perceived cyclic configurations.

In Figure 9, the seven first notes of the cycle oscillate around the cyclic PC $b' \circ c'$ described by:

$$\text{rhyt} = 1 \circ \text{rhyt} = 2 \\ \text{diat} = 0$$

Then appears a more specific cycle $d' \circ e'$ described by

$$\text{rhyt} = 1 \circ \text{rhyt} = 2 \\ \text{diat} = +1 \quad \text{diat} = 0$$

and is generalized after four notes to cycle $d'' \circ f'$ that does not feature the unison interval any more:

$$\text{rhyt} = 1 \circ \text{rhyt} = 2 \\ \text{diat} = +1$$

Moreover, following the rule of generalization of generalized patterns explained in paragraph 3.5, the more general cycle $b' - c'$ too needs to be generalized into a cycle $b'' - g'$ where the unison interval has been discarded:

$$\text{rhyt} = 1 \circ \text{rhyt} = 2.$$

These different cycles are actually perceived by the listener. Moreover, the integration of this phenomenon into the model helps insuring the relevance of the results and avoiding numerous unwanted combinatorial redundancies.

4.4. The Figure/Ground Rule

Another kind of redundancy appears when occurrences of a pattern, such as the melodic-rhythmic pattern c in figure 10, described by $\text{diat} = -2$ and $\text{rhyt} = 1$ are superposed to a cyclic pattern (b'), such that the pattern (c) is more specific than the cycle period b' , which is simply rhythmic: $\text{rhyt} = 1$. In this case, the intervals that follow these occurrences are identical, since they are related to the same state (b') of the cyclic pattern. Logically the pattern could be extended by the successive extensions of

the cyclic patterns (leading to patterns *d*, *e*, etc.). This phenomenon, which may frequently appear in a musical piece, would lead to another combinatorial proliferation of redundant structures if not correctly controlled by relevant mechanisms. On the contrary, following the *Gestalt* Figure/Ground rule, listeners tend to perceive the pattern *c* as a specific figure that emerges above the periodic background. Following this rule, the figure cannot be extended (into *d*) by a description that can be simply identified to a background extension.

Figure 10. Pattern *c* is a specific figure, above a background generated by the cyclic pattern *b'*.

5. RESULTS

This model was first developed as a library of *OpenMusic* [1]. A new version will be included in the next version 2.0 of *MIDIttoolbox* [4], a *Matlab* toolbox dedicated to music analysis. The model can analyze monodic musical pieces (i.e., constituted by a series of non-superposed notes) and highlight the discovered patterns on a score.

5.1. Examples

Thanks to the complex modeling of listening strategies, the automated analysis system is able to offer a clear pattern description of simple musical pieces, corresponding mostly to actually perceived structures.

5.1.1. Beginning of Mozart Sonata in A K 331

For instance, the analysis of the first theme of Mozart *Sonata in A K 331* (figure 11) shows the basic pattern (*a*), repeated and diatonically transposed, and the 4-measure main phrase (*b*) repeated twice as antecedent and consequent. However, a slight rhythmic transformation at the end of the first occurrence, which our system cannot abstract for the moment, does not allow a discovery of the whole phrase (*b'*). Is also shown the successive repetition of a simple rhythm featuring an eight-note and a fourth-note, leading to a cyclic pattern (*c*). The graduation shows the beginning of each new phase of the cycle, but does not necessarily correspond to perceived segmentations, as explained in previous section. A detailed description of the cyclic pattern discovered by the system has been presented in Figure 9. Interestingly enough, the same algorithm is able to discover 4-measures long phrases as well as simple successions of ascending (*e*) and decreasing (*d* and *f*) conjunct lines.

Figure 11. Automated analysis of first theme of Mozart *Sonata in A K 331*.

5.1.2. Geisslerlied

Figure 12 presents the resulting analysis of a medieval song called *Geisslerlied* that the linguist Nicolas Ruwet [11], in one of the first and most famous attempt to model motivic analysis, proposed as a first application of his method. Our model is the first computational system able to offer a relevant and compact analysis of this piece. The piece considered here is however a slight simplification of the actual piece presented by Ruwet, which includes several local motivic variations that our model cannot handle for the moment. Moreover, due to the presence of a suffix of pattern *B* just before its two successive whole occurrences, our model unifies these three occurrences as a cycled pattern and cannot segment properly at the end of each line of the score. The expected segmentation needs the integration of new concepts such as hierarchical segmentation.

Figure 12. Analysis of a *Geisslerlied* (slightly simplified) [11].

Neither these levels of precision or of perceptive relevance have been achieved before. Others pattern discovery systems would indeed include a numerous set of redundant patterns such as suffixes or redundant extensions. This shows the necessity of mechanisms of adaptive redundancy filtering such as those proposed in this paper. However the analyses remain significantly restricted, as numerous aspects of musical expression have not been

taken into account yet.

5.2. Algorithm Complexity

The algorithm complexity may be expressed along two dimensions. First, through the complexity of discovered structures: proliferation of redundant patterns, for instance, would lead to combinatorial explosion, since each new structure needs proper processes assessing their interrelationships with the other structures, and inferring their possible extensions. Hence a maximally compact description insures in the same time the clarity and relevance of the results and the limitation of combinatorial explosion. Complexity may be considered also with respect to the technical implementation of the modeling. Our proposed algorithms remain yet in a draft version and are for the time being only partially optimized. Yet the modeling has been conceived with the constant objective to minimize computational costs. Hence the identification of similar descriptions is based on hash tables, as explained in paragraph 2.3.2, which insure optimal time complexity.

6. CURRENT RESEARCHES

Thanks to this perceptive mimicry, the model offers promising results. Yet bad behaviors need to be controlled, and a large scope of musical expression – such as polyphony – has not been taken into account yet.

6.1. Addition of Segmentation Principles

The structures currently found are based solely on pattern repetitions. Should be added another mechanism founded on the merging of notes closed in time or pitch domain, and, reversely, on segmentation between distant notes, following *Gestalt* rules of proximity and similarity [8] [2]. Although this rule plays a significant role in the perception of large-scale musical structures, there is no common agreement on its application to detailed structure, because it highly depends on the subjective choice of musical parameters used for the segmentations [3]. We propose to investigate the competitive/collaborative interrelations between the two rules of pattern discovery and *Gestalt* segmentation. For instance, a pattern repetition may be masked due to an important temporal gap within one of the occurrences.

6.2. Detection of Musical Transformations

Our model is able to detect not only exact repetitions of patterns, but also partial repetitions along particular musical dimensions, leading to the discovery of interesting structures. Yet other aspects of musical transformations should be considered too, such as the local insertion or deletion of notes. Solutions have been proposed [10], based on dynamic programming and edit distance, allowing optimal alignment between similar notes of each occurrence. We expect our methodology to offer new solutions to these

problems, funded on complex modeling of detailed cognitive strategies.

6.3. From Monody to Polyphony

Our approach is limited to the detection of repeated monodic patterns (i.e. sequences of successive notes) within a monodic musical piece. Music, in general, is polyphonic: it can contain simultaneous notes forming chords, in particular, and simultaneous monodic lines forming different voices. Researches have been carried out in this domain [9], focused on the discovery of repeated exact patterns along different pre-specified dimensions. We are currently developing rules of automated discovery of melodic lines inside polyphonic sets of notes (or stream segregation), based on cognitive heuristics. Our study will then focus on the interactions between pattern discovery and stream segregation. We will then extend the scope by considering pattern of chords, which will need a formalizing of a general concept of interval between successive chords.

6.4. Applications to Musical Databases

The automated discovery of repeated patterns can be directly applied to automated indexing of musical content in symbolic music databases. This approach may be generalized later to audio databases, once robust and general tools for automated transcription of musical sound into symbolic scores will be available. A new kind of similarity distance between musical pieces may be defined, based on these pattern descriptions, offering new ways of browsing inside a music database using pattern-based similarity distance.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Assayag, C. Rueda, M. Laurson, C. Agon, and O. Delerue. Computer assisted composition at ircam: From patchwork to openmusic. *Computer Music Journal*, 23(3):59–72, 1999.
- [2] E. Cambouropoulos. *Towards a General Computational Theory of Musical Structure*. PhD thesis, University of Edinburgh, 1998.
- [3] I. Deliège. Grouping conditions in listening to music: An approach to lerdahl and jackendoffs grouping preference rules. *Music Perception*, 4(4):325–350, 1987.
- [4] T. Eerola and P. Toiviainen. Mir in matlab: The midi toolbox. In *Proceedings of the 2004 International Conference on Music Information Retrieval*, 2004.
- [5] B. Ganter and R. Wille. *Formal Concept Analysis: Mathematical Foundations*. Springer-Verlag, 1999.

- [6] O. Lartillot. A multi-parametric and redundancy-filtering approach to pattern identification. In *Proceedings of the 2004 International Conference on Music Information Retrieval*, 2004a.
- [7] O. Lartillot. An adaptive multi-parametric and redundancy-filtering approach for motivic pattern discovery. In *Proceedings of the 2004 International Conference on Sound and Music Computing*, 2004b.
- [8] F. Lerdahl and R. Jackendoff. *A Generative Theory of Tonal Music*. The M.I.T. Press, 1983.
- [9] D. Meredith, K. Lemström, and G.A. Wiggins. Algorithms for discovering repeated patterns in multidimensional representations of polyphonic music. *Journal of New Music Research*, 31(4):321–345, 2002.
- [10] P.-Y. Rolland. Discovering patterns in musical sequences. *Journal of New Music Research*, 28:334–350, 1999.
- [11] N. Ruwet. Methods of analysis in musicology. *Music Analysis*, 6(1-2):4–39, 1987.
- [12] M. Zaki. Efficient algorithms for mining closed itemsets and their lattice structure. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 17(4):462–478, 2005.